

SCIENTIFIC IMPORTANCE OF PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH IN THE SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH

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The article addresses important issues such as the development of science, the formation of youth spirituality, the factors that shape the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation, scientific heritage, philosophical knowledge, national and universal heritage, which is the basis of philosophical worldview.

Key words: spirituality, enlightenment, culture, consciousness, science, thinking, worldview, values, upbringing, ideology, humanity, patriotism

В статье затрагиваются такие важные вопросы, как развитие науки, формирование духовности молодежи, факторы, формирующие воспитание гармонично развитого поколения, научное наследие, философское знание, национальное и общечеловеческое наследие, являющееся основой философского мировоззрения.

Ключевые слова: духовность, просвещение, культура, сознание, наука, мышление, мировоззрение, ценности, воспитание, мировоззрение, гуманизм, патриотизм

Мақолада илм фан тараққиёти, ёшлар маънавиятини шаклланиши, баркамол авлод тарбиясини шакллантирувчи омиллар, илмий мерос, фалсафий билим, фалсафий дунёқарашга асос бўлувчи миллий ва умуминсоний мерос каби муҳим масалалар тилга олинган.

Калит сўзлар: маънавият, маърифат, маданият, онг, илм, тафаккур, дунёқараш, қадрият, тарбия, мафкура, инсонпарварлик, ватанпарварлик

The issue of philosophical knowledge and reliance on the scientific worldview in the formation of youth spirituality, improving the quality of education and strengthening the capacity of personnel in the development of world science is being studied as an important and necessary problem not only of social sciences and humanities. The issue of philosophy, philosophical knowledge and scientific worldview, along with epistemological principles such as humanism and patriotism, is actively studied in the system of social sciences and humanities, explaining the need to further develop the object and subject of its study on the basis of modern scientific methods.

We have set ourselves the great goal of building the foundations of the Third Renaissance in our country, for which we must create an environment and conditions that will educate new Khorezmians, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Ulugbeks, Navoi and Baburs.¹

History has always shown that the younger generation, on whom we rely today and in the future, must not worry about its spiritual maturity. These processes are directly related to the use of the spiritual heritage of the ancestors and the effective functioning of today's educational and upbringing processes. It means that we are all equally responsible for the

¹<https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4057>. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis 29.12.2020

spiritual maturity of the youth. The upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation, the concept of a perfect human being means that serious attention should be paid to every aspect of education, and the consciousness of the younger generation plays an important role in shaping its worldview.

Spiritual perfection, in turn, is the main criterion for the young generation to be patriotic, loyal to the people, humane, kind, disciplined, respecting the pride of the nation, preserving the traditions and scientific heritage of our great ancestors, becoming a morally pure person.

Today, in addition to the positive aspects of science around the world, there are also some negative issues. As science and enlightenment develop in most countries of the world, wars and conflicts in some countries, spiritual poverty, environmental problems, hunger and thirst, and the proliferation of various diseases affect not only the development of one's own country but also the development of other countries. endangering. Such situations in the world community evoke a sense of wonder and admiration among people of all common sense. The reforms being carried out in the field of education in our country show how important it is to prevent these problems. We all know that the processes of globalization, in particular, the spiritual harmony that is formed during the life experiences of human relationships, are of great importance today. This means that man shapes and develops his spirituality from the moment he realizes himself as a person to the end of his life.

The issue of educating young people, who are the future of the development of our country, as a comprehensively mature and spiritually mature person, is in the center of attention of our state as a strategic issue. Considering that the majority of the population of Uzbekistan is under 30 years old, one of the most pressing issues today is to educate this young generation as a fully developed spiritually mature person, able to compete with the youth of developed countries. Because young people have higher philosophical knowledge and scientific outlook, spiritual perfection and determination than ever before.

“We have set ourselves the great goal of building the foundations of the Third Renaissance in our country, for which we must create an environment and conditions that will educate new Khorezmians, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Ulugbeks, Navoi and Baburs. At the same time, first of all, the development of education and upbringing, healthy lifestyle decisions, the development of science and innovation should serve as the main pillars of our national idea.

To achieve this goal, our young people must set great goals, create ample opportunities for them to achieve them and provide all possible assistance - this should be a priority for all of us. Only then will our children become a great and powerful force that will realize the age-old dreams of our people.² “

In this regard, the first President Islam Karimov, who praised the views of foreign experts, who are highly valued by young people, puts forward the following views“...talking to our young people, he wishes that we could see and work with such young people in other countries, who have mastered their profession and are fluent in foreign languages. In short, they appreciate the potential of the youth of Uzbekistan. Indeed, it is a sign that a new generation of thinkers, no less than anyone else in any field, is emerging. It is absolutely appropriate to use this phrase for thousands of our young men and women who are determined to move forward with pure intentions, to mobilize their God-given opportunities

²<https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4057>Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis 29.12.2020

and potential for the development of Uzbekistan, and therefore, first of all, to agree and find a place in life. that is, the eyes of such young people are burning, and the desire to act is so firm and courageous, give me a chance, I will show myself, to live such children with pride, say, do not love, do not love, create all the conditions for them I ask myself if it is possible not to give.³ In the Western world, individualism and self-interest prevail over collective bargaining⁴. Therefore, in order to prevent this situation, our state is taking certain measures to preserve and develop the centuries-old tolerance, justice, devotion, kindness, high cultural heritage, rich customs and traditions.

It is emphasized that the first important issue is the liberalization of all spheres of political life, state and society building. If the state does not liberate itself, it cannot liberate spiritual life. In this regard, a number of works are being carried out in our country.

We have a lot of traditions and timeless traditions for the development of spiritual and moral upbringing of the younger generation left by our ancestors. It is expedient to use this heritage in the spiritual upbringing of the younger generation. Because we must always keep in mind that the future of our state depends on how our young generation develops and what spiritual qualities they grow up to have, how they are actively involved and what high goals they serve. The work carried out in the country to reform the education system is aimed at the same goal. From the ideological point of view, this issue is in line with the principles of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education in the new edition. The ideological harmony of the modern educational system and the national heritage also means the need to rely on the spiritual and enlightenment foundations of the national heritage in the educational process.

From this point of view, the rich spiritual heritage created by our great ancestors, scholars and thinkers over the centuries has not lost its place in educating the younger generation in the spirit of perfection. Today, it is very important to inculcate feelings and concepts related to parents, family and neighborhood, historical memory, national pride, perfect human upbringing through effective methods in the hearts and minds of the younger generation.

In order for the younger generation to grow up with a perfect, strong-willed, pure conscience in all respects, first of all, it is important to raise our spiritual and enlightenment activities to a high level. The spiritual maturity of the youth, our harmoniously developed generation is our main goal. One of our main goals in achieving this is to intensify all educational activities in the process of education and upbringing of the younger generation in the formation of spiritual maturity in their minds.

Where great scholars and thinkers, saints, grow up, first of all, the centers of science, enlightenment, culture and spirituality must be developed. A great civilization will never emerge in an empty space. It is imperative that everyone carefully, respects, honors, carefully studies the values created by their ancestors and contemporaries, uses them creatively and critically, enriches them with content and shapes them.

At the same time, there are also political forces and movements that are currently seeking to expand their sphere of influence through ideological means. Therefore, in order to restore the national image, national spirit and national pride of our people today, we must study the

³Karimov.I.A., To serve for the happiness and great future of our motherland is the highest happiness. T.: "Uzbekistan" 2015 245-p

⁴Karimov.I.A., High spirituality is an invincible force, T.: Spirituality, 2008 10-p

ancient traditions, history, culture, art, culture and moral views of the people and pass them on to the younger generation. National pride, national pride, human values are all connected with the process of education and upbringing.

“In this regard, it is appropriate to state the following views of our President “We bring up young people as independent and logical thinkers, with noble qualities, based on modern knowledge and experience, national and universal values.”⁵.

After all, no nation can respect the values of other nations without understanding its identity, without preserving its national culture and national values. The strength of independent Uzbekistan lies in the commitment of our people to universal values. For centuries, our people have been carefully preserving the delicate buds of justice, equality and humanity for future generations. The ultimate goal of renewing Uzbekistan is to revive these traditions, to give them a new meaning, to create the necessary conditions for peace, prosperity, culture, freedom of conscience and the perfection of everyone in our land. Teaching young people universal and national values and teaching them to respect them will determine how our values will be valued in the future.

Today's youth must be spiritually well-educated professionals, enthusiastic about their people, and have a deep knowledge of our national values. Mankind lives and develops based on historical experience and the heritage of its ancestors, new ideas never arise spontaneously, they arise from the bases of the past. Mankind has reached the current stage of development of society due to the rich heritage of the past. The secrets of unparalleled upbringing created by our ancestors, their teachings on morality have been tested by life experience and have acquired a universal essence.

Philosophical philosophical knowledge and approaches contribute to increasing a person's spiritual potential by teaching him or her to critically analyze, especially the younger generation. The philosophical approach is the process of analyzing the information received by man, assimilating it through the methods of categorical reflexive and methodical selection. Because it causes it to find its place. It is an internal need of a person to process this information and analyze the problems of man and the world in it. Philosophy plays an important role in the life of man and society, shaping these aspects of man. This takes into account the national characteristics of the philosophical approach, the characteristics of the system of governance of the state and society in social relations.

Leaving aside four or five years to get a deeper understanding of what philosophy really is, one doesn't even have a life. Because he has very deep wisdom. Wisdom, on the other hand, is the science of knowing this essence, the Truth, and loving it. However, devoting a lifetime to it is the most valuable thing for a person. One who seeks to know the essence and achieves his goal along the way is one of the happiest people in the world.

The main goal of the philosophical approach is to have a certain knowledge base at a young age, only after they have developed skills such as analyzing, interpreting and understanding philosophical texts, it is possible to know to what extent they have mastered the basic concepts and philosophical methods. This is achieved by differentiating between philosophical and non-philosophical issues, analyzing problems, defining relationships, and understanding that young people have formed the skills to determine their spiritual maturity.

⁵<https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4057>Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis 29.12.2020

In addition, the correct use of words in the expression of one's thoughts in oral and written speech implies a step-by-step aspiration to the goal.

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